

THE EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF PREPREG TACK

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SUMMARY

Automated tape laying (ATL) success is heavily dependent on prepreg tack. A new test is presented determining values for tack and compliance. The test is then utilised to determine the effect of those operational variables which have been seen to dominate performance. Comparisons with traditional resin probe tests reveal a vacuum component not previously mentioned in prepreg tack research.

Keywords: ATL, AFP, prepreg, tack, drape, PSA, pressure sensitive, adhesive, peel test, probe test, reptation, WLF, rheology, extensional rheology, viscosity, polymer melt.

INTRODUCTION

Modern robotic layup processes such as automated tape laying (ATL), have demonstrated a sensitivity to prepreg tack levels [1]. A comprehensive search reveals the absence of a commercial standardised method for determining prepreg tack [2]. Methods such as the BS EN1464:1994 floating roller method and probe tack test [3] have been utilised by the pressure sensitive adhesives (PSA) industry. Typically prepreg tack levels are specified by manufacturers as simply high, medium or low, utilising a subjective touch test in conjunction with a probe or roller method. ATL is currently utilised in the aerospace industry using lightweight (< 300gsm) carbon prepreg. However, ATL is now being developed for wind turbine rotor blade production requiring heavier weight (up to 1600gsm) E-glass fabrics and low cost matrix. Therefore, a new test and greater understanding of tack is required to aid with the development of cost-efficient ATL materials and rapid automated manufacture.

For ATL production prepreg is supplied on a roll with backing paper on one side. The backing paper is used to convey the material and retain the prepreg during the cutting of small intricate sections. As the material passes through the delivery head it is cut and applied to the mould under pressure provided by the compaction shoe. The unbroken backing paper is then returned to a take up spool (Figure 1). Simplified modelling of the ATL process (Figure 2) reveals that the peeling mechanism is most prevalent during normal operation. The peel mechanism is driven by backing paper tack and opposed by

the stiffness of the prepreg material. Therefore, an indication of both material stiffness and peel tack is desirable to determine suitability for automated manufacture. Shear forces on the prepreg are avoided by accurate control of backing paper tension.

A number of operating parameters can be adjusted during the ATL process and are known to affect tack. In particular a heat gun can be integrated into the delivery head as increased temperatures have been seen to increase prepreg tack [1]. Operating parameters which can be adjusted during production and have been investigated include:-

- Feed rate (typical range 0-50 m/min)
- Compaction force (typical value 265-1300N for a 150mm wide roller)
- Temperature (typical ambient-80°C)
- Use of mould release agents
- Mould surface finish

Previous prepreg-specific tack research is limited and is typically utilised to assist with materials development, for example the floating roller method has shown that the level of cure can have an effect on prepreg tack [2]. Multiple studies of probe testing have concluded that viscoelastic properties of the material are key to understanding tack [4], with some continuing to make accurate predictions of experimental results based on bulk viscoelastic properties [5], yet none have characterised tack response to operational variables typically seen during automated manufacture. However, the study of tack within the PSA industry is much more comprehensive. Failure modes during probe testing have been described and predictions made based on fracture mechanisms and viscoelastic principles [3]. Viscoelastic windows and master curves using time-temperature superposition have been used to determine a resin's suitability as a PSA adhesive [6]. However, PSA research is restricted to the peel and application rates provided by hand actuation and neglects the presence of fibres within the resin. Therefore, it would be beneficial to assess the relevance of PSA theories and practices to prepreg tack.

Figure 1. A typical example of an ATL prepreg tape dispensing head [1].

Figure 2. The peel mechanism experienced by ATL tape during normal operation.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Apparatus

The peel tack test rig utilises a series of rollers mounted to the base of a mechanical test device. The upper jaw is fitted with a clamp which accommodates a 75mm wide sample (Figure 3). Stainless steel plates are used to simulate the mould surface. The prepreg material and simulated mould surface are drawn through a set of spring loaded rollers peeling at 90°. The first 160mm of material has backing paper on both sides and is used to record material compliance. The last 140mm of material has the mould side of backing paper removed and is used to record tack and compliance (Figure 4). The pull force is recorded using a mechanical test rig with 1kN load cell.

Figure 3. Prototype ATL peel test rig mounted within a mechanical test rig

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the peel test.

Analysis

An average value is calculated for both compliance and tack & compliance. Tack is calculated by subtracting compliance from tack & compliance average values (Figure 5). Typically batches of 3-5 samples are tested. A statistical analysis can also reveal sample variance and batch variance indicating tack uniformity. Small corrections are also made to account for bearing friction and the absence of a layer of backing paper within the tack & compliance readings.

Figure 5. Typical tack results recording compliance and tack.

RESULTS

Tests were repeated on multiple occasions to prove the validity and repeatability of the method, returning maximum errors of 5% and 16% for compliance and tack. Unidirectional (UD) samples showed greater repeatability than multidirectional fabrics. Several sources of error such as creases and oscillatory plate motion could be reduced by careful handling and positioning of the sample. Significant tack variability within the

prepreg roll was seen. Therefore, in the present work experimental analysis has been restricted to the isolation of a single variable during each experiment.

Effect of Operational Variables

A complete DOE of operational variables was conducted using a commercial UD 1600gsm E-glass fibre epoxy prepreg. The results for the effect of variables revealed that release agents, temperature and feed rates had the largest effect on tack (Table 1). Release agents formed a barrier to prevent adequate contact between the specimen and rigid plate, mostly eliminating tack. Future values for tack testing were chosen which recorded a high tack result whilst accurately reflecting the ATL process and facilitating a quick test with minimal preparation (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of process variables on prepreg tack of 1600gsm UD glass fibre prepreg.

Process Variable	Max. Effect (%)	Avg. Error (%)	Tack Relationship	Chosen Test Rig Settings
Release Agents	99.5	7.3	Decrease	None
Feed Rate	96.8	11.4	Increase	500mm/min
Temperature	95.2	3.1	Decrease	20°C
Compaction Force	36.7	11.5	Decrease	100N
Surface Finish	27.5	32	Increase	STD \approx Ra0.2 μ m

Effect of Resin Type

To confirm that results are in accordance with manufacturer’s current tack specifications of high, medium and low, three specimens were prepared with equal fibre architecture and volume fraction. The results show a stable value for compliance and tack levels which follow the manufacturer’s specified trend of low-high (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Tack test results for prepreg specimens of equal fibre architecture with high, medium and low tack resins as specified by manufacturer.

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

Failure Modes

Two failure modes were observed during testing, wet failure was observed in liquid-like resin leading to the formation of resin strands. Such strands eventually fail depositing a significant amount of resin on the rigid plate. Dry failure occurs in stiffer materials with little or no resin deposition seen on the rigid plate (Figure 7). These two modes of failure, termed cohesive and interfacial, have previously been observed during probe tack testing [7]. Earlier experiments with peel testing have revealed two additional modes of stick-slip and glassy fracture [8]. These failure modes are believed to be associated with resin separation at the backing paper which was not observed here.

Figure 7. Failure modes with dry or interfacial failure (Left) and wet or cohesive failure (Right).

Temperature Effects

The effect of temperature on the prepreg tack of UD 1600gsm glass fibre epoxy was significant (95.2%). A decrease in prepreg tack with elevated temperatures was recorded (Figure 8). Typically heat guns are fitted to ATL machines to increase temperature thought to increase tack levels. Therefore, the recorded decrease in tack was unexpected and opposed to industrial experience. Since UD1600gsm is not a typical ATL material the experiment was repeated with carbon 268gsm ATL prepreg (Figure 9). A resulting increase in prepreg tack was observed. The failure mode was found to differ from wet cohesive failure in the UD1600 to dry interfacial failure in the Carbon ATL prepreg. Tack levels were compared to viscosity levels for the resin and found that the trend was comparable (Figure 8). Therefore, during wet failure the viscoelastic properties are thought to govern tack levels. However, no such trend could be observed in the dry failure of ATL carbon prepreg where tack was found to increase through improved surface wetting.

Figure 8. Temperature effects on 1600gsm UD E-glass prepreg tack compared to resin viscosity.

Figure 9. Temperature effects on ATL carbon prepreg tack.

Temperature Effects on Tack Compared to Probe Testing

To validate the peel test temperature results, probe testing was conducted with a standard 40mm diameter aluminium probe with a 10N initial application force dwelled at a fixed extension for 10s. Results of UD 1600gsm E-glass fibre epoxy prepreg material complimented the peel test results showing reduced tack with increasing temperature at several peel rates (Figure 10). However, when testing neat resin from UD1600gsm prepreg, results revealed a rise in tack levels contradicting peel and probe results for prepreg. The rise in tack corresponded to the temperature at which the material fully wet-out the probe surface. Therefore, the rise in tack may be attributed to a vacuum pressure force. To confirm this theory a vacuum-less probe test was developed which allowed an inflow of air beneath the probe surface. The results show no increase in resin tack with increased temperature (Figure 11). Further confirmation was found in the presence of air bubbles in the resin following the vacuum-less probe test at increased temperatures. The increase in resin tack with increased temperature is seen only in traditional probe testing with neat resin and is therefore attributed to vacuum pressure. This rise in tack is not seen in the prepreg sample, indicating that the fibres create a textured surface which allows greater airflow.

Figure 10. Tack of 1600 UD E-glass prepreg as a function of temperature and peel rate.

Figure 11. Standard probe test compared to vacuum-less probe test results and vacuum-less probe test equipment showing solid-like resin behaviour and poor surface wetting at 20°C (Left) in comparison to viscoelastic behaviour and fully wetted surface at 35°C (Right).

Feed Rate Effects

Isolating the effect of feed rate on tack revealed a significant increase in prepreg tack (96.8%). A wet failure mode is observed with greater resin deposition at low feed rates. Therefore, tack levels are anticipated to be governed by the resins viscoelastic properties. In such instances, time-temperature superposition using the William-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation is potentially possible [9] and has been applied successfully in

peel adhesion tests for many years [6]. The increased tack level response to increased feed rate follows stress relaxation trends where increased temperature gives similar effects to increased experiment time (reduced feed rates). However, comparing the results calculated using the WLF equation based on standard rheological data reveals an underestimation of experimental tack levels for lower feed rates (Figure 12). An overestimation of tack force could easily be explained by the onset of interfacial failure due to reduced contact time at higher feed rates. However, an underestimation of tack force may only be explained by strain hardening which is not detected in a traditional rheological test. Such strain hardening is predicted by the reptation model indicating that a molten polymer exhibits strain hardening behaviour and can even behave like a cross-linked polymer at high strain rates [10]. This effect is rarely seen at the strain rates typically used during standard rheological testing [11]. Therefore, extensional rheology may increase prediction accuracy of wet failure feed rate effects. As the feed rate increases the WLF equation now over-predicts the tack as some dry interfacial failure is now believed to occur.

Figure 12. Experimental feed rate effects on tack compared to those calculated using the WLF equation and traditional rheological data.

CONCLUSIONS

A new peel tack test has been developed with the advantage that no separate application stage is required, more accurately reflecting the ATL process. Values are recorded for material compliance and tack levels giving the user two production related quantities signifying ease of forming and retention of prepreg to the mould surface. The test could be performed without cleaning and preparation quickly and easily using disposable plates to simulate the mould surface. Statistical analysis gives the user an idea of sample and batch variance and therefore tack uniformity of the material.

The new test has been utilised to quantify the effects of ATL operational variables such as temperature, feed rate, surface finish, compaction pressure and use of mould release agents on the tack of 1600gsm UD E-glass fibre epoxy. The effect of each variable was found to be dependent on the observed failure mode. Two distinct modes were observed as dry surface failure, due to poor contact, and wet failure within the resin, due to a

weak cohesive force. Additionally, a mixture of the two modes could be seen in patches over a single sample. The failure mode can be determined by resin deposition and surface wetting, an observed maximum for wet failure.

Increased temperature was found to increase tack during dry failure but decrease during wet failure. The tack levels were found to follow rheological data trends during wet failure but not dry. Increasing temperature allows increased flow and surface contact, increasing surface wetting, but weakening the internal strength of the resin. Therefore, it is predicted that a peak tack level maybe observed at the transition of failure modes, where internal strength and surface wetting are both maximised. The WLF equation predicts that the same effect will be observed for changes in feed rate. Mould release agents completely eliminated tack, switching wet failure to dry failure by introducing a barrier layer preventing surface adhesion.

Considering these results the use of the viscoelastic windows principle used in PSA can only be applied to operating conditions which have a wet failure. This wet failure would correspond to a contact efficient PSA lying below the Dahlquist criteria line. Changes in operational conditions such as temperature feed rate and mould releases cause the prepreg to become contact inefficient. Additionally, strain hardening effects of molten polymers may prevent the use of the WLF equation with typical rheological data, requiring extensional or actual tack data for time-temperature super positioning. Therefore the extensive operational range of ATL prepreg requires a tack principle theory which is inclusive of both internal viscoelastic and surface interface failure mechanisms.

Validation of the peel test was also carried out with a traditional probe tack test. Results for prepreg confirmed the reduction in tack with increasing temperature. However, traditional probe testing of resin alone revealed an increase in tack with temperature. Development of a vacuum-less probe test revealed this rise to be a result of vacuum pressure found at the onset of complete surface wetting. Since this rise was not detected in the prepreg sample it is apparent that the fibres allow greater airflow. Therefore, probe testing of resin alone cannot be used to indicate prepreg tack in the case of complete surface wetting.

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